

**PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE UTERUS IN CORONAVIRUS
INFECTION AND ITS EFFECT ON THE FETUS AND BABY**

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Abstract: *Pregnant women have a special place among the risk groups for COVID-19. It is known that pregnancy, although a physiological condition, is associated with changes in a number of organs and systems, including the immune system. Therefore, susceptibility to infections during pregnancy is significantly increased.*

Key words: *pregnant, coronavirus infection, immune, pregnancy*

Currently, surveillance of pregnant women infected with COVID-19 is insufficient, but some observations in China, the United States, and Russia suggest some conclusions. Thus, pregnant women with various extragenital diseases are at high risk, especially in the second half of pregnancy.

A risk factor for complications during pregnancy is a severe obstetric history. Risk factors include preeclampsia in previous pregnancies, high blood pressure, bleeding, coagulation disorders, premature births, termination of pregnancy, and various surgical procedures. Such pregnancies are at risk and require special attention. COVID-19 is more dangerous in the second and third trimesters, which is explained by an increase in the load on various systems of the body. All pregnant women, regardless of coronavirus, should be screened at the intervals specified in the pregnancy protocol. Timely tests, ultrasound examinations, and consultations with physicians are required. Not to miss an obstetric screening test is a guarantee of reducing obstetric and neonatal complications.

Chinese doctors did not detect a new coronavirus in infants of mothers infected with COVID-19 during pregnancy. Data from these patients were published in the journal *Frontiers in Pediatrics*. Although there are four cases reported in the article, it is possible that pregnant women do not transmit the virus to their children. Samples for coronavirus in children were taken from the nasopharynx three days after birth. Fever, cough, and diarrhea were not observed in newborns. At the time of discharge, neither mother nor children (including children who had not been tested for SARS-CoV-2) showed no signs of infection. Summarizing these data, the authors concluded that COVID-19 is unlikely to be transmitted from mother to child, but not at all. Should breastfeeding be discontinued if the mother is diagnosed with coronavirus?

If the mother is suspected of having COVID-19 or has been in contact with patients, she should not stop breastfeeding. However, if a woman has a high fever or other signs of a viral infection and her doctor has prescribed medications that can pass through breast milk and have a harmful effect on the baby, breastfeeding should be stopped during treatment. During this period, it is important to maintain lactation by breastfeeding and continue breastfeeding after recovery.

How can pregnant women protect themselves from COVID-19?

Pregnant women are just as vulnerable as normal people should be justified. The spread of COVID-19 can be stopped by coughing at the elbow and avoiding contact with sick people by washing hands frequently with soap and water or alcohol-based hand sanitizers.

Treatment of pregnant women is based on the incidence of COVID-19, its clinical manifestations, and accurate assessment of obstetric status.

Obstetric tactics depend on several factors: the patient's condition, the condition of the fetus and the duration of pregnancy. Given the high risk of perinatal complications in severe and moderate pregnancies up to 12 weeks of gestation, termination of pregnancy is recommended after treatment of the infectious process. If the patient refuses to terminate the pregnancy, a chorionic biopsy is needed to detect chromosomal abnormalities in the fetus.

Termination of pregnancy and delivery during the development of the disease are associated with maternal mortality and a number of complications: exacerbation of the underlying disease, development and exacerbation of respiratory failure, obstetric hemorrhage, intranatal death, increased septic complications.

If rapid termination is required, vacuum extraction or obstetric clamps may be appropriate. Cesarean section is performed under absolute obstetric instructions, as well as in a dying woman (to save the life of the fetus).

The condition of the mother and child depends on the duration of the disease, the presence of a premorbid background (smoking, obesity, background diseases of the respiratory system and ENT organs, diabetes, HIV infection), the severity of the infection, complications and timely initiation of antiviral therapy.

Thus, rational approaches and well-chosen obstetric and general therapeutic tactics can help save the life and health of mother and child.

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